

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF “SCENARIO-BASED TEACHING” IN DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF SCRIPTWRITERS

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Abstract. This article discusses the foundations for applying the “Scenario-Based Teaching” methodology in developing the professional skills of scriptwriters, highlighting its effective aspects. Based on the analysis of research conducted on the “Scenario-Based Teaching” method, a set of recommendations has been developed.

Keywords: script, scriptwriter, “Scenario-Based Teaching”, professional competence, knowledge, skills, proficiency.

Analyzing academic research and methodological works related to the scenario-based teaching method in the context of developing students’ scriptwriting skills, studying the current state of the field, and incorporating advanced practices into both research and educational activities are purposeful and effective measures. These actions are important for the concrete implementation of the objectives and tasks set in the research.

The scenario-based teaching methodology is a method of delivering educational sessions on the basis of scripts and has been extensively studied in academic research.

Scenario-based teaching aligns with the theories of constructivism and experiential learning. Within this methodology:

- students actively participate;
- they analyze situations;
- they make decisions.

This method models “real-life” situations, prompting students to engage in decision-making, problem-solving, and reflective thinking.

The scenario-based teaching methodology is applied in the following contexts:

- in education and professional development in fields such as philology, pedagogy, medical education, and technical sciences;
- in the process of developing decision-making and problem-solving skills;
- in inclusive education.

A group of educators has noted the effectiveness of organizing educational sessions based on the scenario-based teaching methodology. In particular, V.V.Golubkov was the first to apply the scenario-based teaching method in the process of teaching the subject “Literature”, recommending that, during the instruction of works by classical Russian authors in general education schools, the events of a work be divided into small episodes, with each episode developed into a scenario, and that lessons be conducted in this manner [2].

The researcher substantiates the effectiveness of this methodology with the following three arguments:

First, the student gains a deeper understanding of the work, as each episode stands out distinctly, and the student can readily explain these differences;

Second, the characters in the work come to life through the use of the scenario, enabling the student to engage with them as if interacting in real life;

Third, the tasks carried out by the teacher require the student to think independently.

Regarding scenario-based teaching, N.O.Korst, in a study devoted to the analysis of literary works, describes it as “a complex and time-consuming method, yet one of the most comprehensive approaches to the analysis of literary works” [3].

V.G.Maransman, focusing on the analysis of literary works in the development of reading habits among school students, considers it effective to conduct lessons on literary analysis by having students write television scripts for the works being studied [4].

Researcher S.Kh.Yaminova developed scenario-based teaching methods aimed at fostering students’ independent thinking skills [1]. In this approach, both curricular and extracurricular works studied in general education schools are analyzed by having students write scenarios, thereby ensuring their active engagement in the analysis of literary works.

The methodology proposed by the researcher differs from traditional teaching methods in that students are assigned to write a scenario for the most climactic part of a literary work, and the lesson is conducted as a practical exercise. Specifically, students are asked to imagine filming the selected episode and to describe their vision in writing. As a result, students’ imaginative perception of the literary work expands, and they develop a broader sense of its essence. At the same time, this method contributes to the formation of students’ written expression.

In addition, the researcher provided explanations for terminology related to scenarios and, for the first time in Uzbekistan, introduced the term “Scenario-Based

Teaching”. The study identified the distinctive features of the scenario-based teaching method, examined its connections to traditional methods of teaching literature, and established its methodological foundations.

Scenario-based teaching is a distinctive method and is also of significance to our research. This is because, in implementing this method, the teacher provides information on the general requirements for preparing a scenario, thereby developing students’ initial knowledge and skills related to scriptwriting.

The scenario-based teaching methodology is an effective approach aimed at developing students’ professional skills through situations that closely resemble real-life contexts. This methodology engages the student not as a passive listener but as an active participant in the learning process, fostering professional mastery through practical exercises.

According to the research findings, the following effective aspects of the scenario-based teaching methodology in developing students’ scriptwriting skills were identified:

First, the lesson is organized in a non-traditional manner;

Second, students gain a deeper familiarity with the chosen work;

Third, students’ creative and innovative thinking and abilities are developed;

Fourth, students’ capacity for independent work and research is strengthened;

Fifth, students acquire initial knowledge and skills in scriptwriting.

In conclusion, it should be noted that scenario-based teaching is a distinctive method for developing students’ scriptwriting skills and holds significance for our research. The study has identified the effective aspects of this methodology in enhancing students’ abilities in this field.

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